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Developing interdisciplinary engineering education The role of educational leadership

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ABSTRACT

Many Higher Education Institutes intend to implement interdisciplinarity in their engineering programs to help students prepare for future work. Realizing interdisciplinary education is not easy and requires good educational leadership. In former research by Leithwood et al, four broad categories of leadership practices have been identified as important for leadership success: setting direction, developing people, developing the organization, and managing the educational program.

In our research, we study the role of educational leadership in designing and implementing interdisciplinary engineering education. Context is the Smart Solution Semester of Saxion University of Applied Sciences, where third-year students from three or more disciplines work together in project teams on large (25 ECTS) projects, provided by research groups and business partners.

Research questions are:

- How has interdisciplinary engineering education been implemented?
- What were leadership behaviors, practices and actions in this process?

In the first phase of this qualitative, exploratory project, five key stakeholders, identified as being educational leaders, were interviewed through semi-structured interviews, focusing on the educational leadership practices. All interviews were recorded and written down verbatim. Data were coded and analyzed with Atlas.ti. Findings are that all leadership practices were -though not equally- visible;

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Implementation success depends on the amount to which the educational change has been a bottom-up initiative; For interdisciplinary work, it is important to get to know each other's discipline, including the structure of underlying knowledge. Students are not supervised in this process, nor are the teachers working together.

1 INTRODUCTION

To meet the challenges of the future, it is important that engineers are capable of working in interdisciplinary settings. Complex problems in areas such as safety, health, or climate change, do not only require the application of technical and scientific knowledge, but also require the application of 21st century skills such as creativity, complex problem solving, digital skills, reflection, and the collaboration and co-learning of engineers in interdisciplinary teams. Many Higher Education Institutes intend to implement interdisciplinarity in their engineering programs to help students prepare for future work. In Saxion University of Applied Science in the Netherlands, a whole semester in the third year is dedicated to this interdisciplinary work.

Although the importance of interdisciplinary education in engineering programs is acknowledged, realizing it is not easy. It requires educational leaders and teachers of different educational programs to collaborate consistently, since they share the responsibility for the interdisciplinary curriculum. Interactions between teachers provide opportunities to share expertise [1]. In this respect, the way in which teachers are being supported is an important factor [2]. Teachers should not only have an 'interdisciplinary attitude' but should also experience room for strengthening their learning and working together.

Educational leadership influences the successful implementation of (sustainable) educational change [e.g. 3], also specifically in the context of realizing high quality science and engineering education [4].

In our research, we study the role of educational leadership, distributed from formal leaders to teacher leaders, in designing and implementing interdisciplinary engineering education. This is studied in the context of the interdisciplinary semester at Saxion University, in which third-year students from more than one program work together in project teams on large (25 ECTS) projects, provided by research groups and business partners. More information on the semester is provided in section 3.1.

2 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

There are two concepts that are central in this research: interdisciplinarity and educational leadership.

2.1 Interdisciplinarity

What exactly does interdisciplinarity mean? Interdisciplinary challenges do not only require the mere application of knowledge from different disciplines, but also an integrated synthesis of that knowledge. Through combining and integrating knowledge from different disciplines, new knowledge and innovative approaches can evolve through which challenges can be solved more adequately and effectively [5]. Multidisciplinarity, interdisciplinarity and transdisciplinarity can be regarded as placed on a continuum [6], ranging from no or partial integration to full integration of knowledge. When professionals from different disciplines work together, side by side, analyzing and solving the challenge without integrating the different perspectives, this

is called multidisciplinary. Within interdisciplinary settings, knowledge from different disciplines are integrated to construct a new perspective on the situation at hand. Transdisciplinarity refers to the construction of new knowledge that is synthesized from the different disciplines and underlying epistemologies. A new, integrated knowledge field emerges in which learning goals, skills, and concepts transcend disciplinary skills and concepts [7]. The higher on the continuum from isolated to transdisciplinary education, the better 21st century skills, positive student attitudes and teacher enthusiasm are promoted [7]. At the same time, this asks for more teacher involvement, professional development as well as sustainable facilitation by management. The distinction between inter- and transdisciplinary learning is “opaque” [6, p.53], and both terms are used indiscriminately in the literature. In this study, we use the word interdisciplinary.

2.2 Integrated and distributed educational leadership

The quality of the design and structure of interdisciplinary education is impacted by the interactions and (shared) responsibilities between those who are involved in the teaching and design process, and by the way in which these persons are facilitated. Powerful leadership with a clear vision on education and personal commitment are crucial to realizing a new paradigm for science and engineering education [4]. In former research by Leithwood et al [8], four broad categories of leadership practices have been identified as important for leadership success: setting direction (clear vision), developing people, developing the organization, and managing the educational program. The first category, setting direction, permeates in all activities and decisions that are being undertaken. Thus, following others [e.g. 9, 10], Muijenburg et al. [11] distinguish between three core functions of integrated leadership (see table 1). In the literature, increasing attention is being paid to integrated and distributed leadership. The question then becomes, how are activities in the three core practices integrated, and how are these activities distributed between stakeholders?

Table 1 Core functions of educational leadership [11]

Managing the educational program (teaching and learning)	Developing the organization	Understanding and developing people
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a productive work environment for both teachers and students • Monitoring school activities and results • Giving feedback to teachers based on observations of teaching processes • Allocating teachers and support staff to curriculum parts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing a clear vision and goals • Managing the school environment and working conditions • Connecting the school to the community outside the school • The strategic allocation of means 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intellectually stimulating and individually coaching teachers • Setting an example for teachers • Setting HR-policy in the school • Promoting and participating in teacher learning and development

3 RESEARCH APPROACH

3.1 Context

Within Saxion University of Applied Sciences, interdisciplinary education has been implemented in a central semester, in which currently 22 programs participate. The semester initiated within the faculty of Life Sciences, Engineering and Design (LED), which houses bachelor programs in these domains (such as chemical engineering,

electrical engineering, forensic research, biomedical engineering, industrial product design, mechatronics, information science, nanotechnology). LED started the discussion about the need for educational improvement, somewhere 2013-2014. This culminated in the design and development of the then-called 'living technology project. Since its first implementation, the number of programs participating in this interdisciplinary semester is growing, up till 22 per September 2019, including also programs from social or health disciplines. This is one-third of all Saxion bachelor programs. With the growth of the semester, the name changed into Smart Solutions Semester.

In the semester, third-year students from three or more disciplines work together in project teams on large (25 ECTS) projects, provided by research groups and business partners. The size of a student project team varies from 4-8 students. They are supervised by a tutor, focused on the learning and working process. During a time frame of 20 weeks, students work on this project, almost full-time. They meet with their tutor and client regularly, about once a week, not necessarily in the same meeting. In the meantime, they develop their project at Saxion, at the client's office, at home or at any place they feel fit. In-between sessions, they may ask their tutor for support or advice, or they may ask the instructor or another teacher to give a masterclass on a specific subject.

Some examples of projects are: green walls for classrooms, 3D-printing with concrete; early diagnosis of complex diseases (osteoarthritis); Metastasis on a chip; light detecting textiles; collaborative robots in a production environment. Since students come from different disciplines, they are supposed to share views, values, approaches, and knowledge, in order to be able to solve the question at hand. It is the role of the tutor to coach the students on their use of knowledge, research abilities, and their professional behavior (e.g. communication with client; teamwork, work ethos). Tutors do not assess their own groups.

3.2 Research questions

We started an explorative study with the aim to learn more about the design and implementation of interdisciplinary education, as well as the supportive or hindering factors of educational leadership in this process. Data gathering was focused on obtaining rich, descriptive information on both the design and implementation processes and the role of educational leadership in the program, especially in the faculty where it all started. The research questions for this explorative study (and object of this research paper) are:

- Within the faculty of LED, how has interdisciplinary engineering education been implemented?
- Within the faculty of LED, what were leadership behaviors, practices and actions in this process?

3.3 Respondents and data collection

In order to answer the research questions, qualitative interviews were conducted with stakeholders with a leadership role, focusing on their experiences with the semester. Semi-structured interviews were conducted late 2018 and early 2019. The focus was on the integrated leadership practices. The dean of the faculty identified 5 respondents, who were to be interviewed: a team leader (TL), head teacher (HT), researcher (RE), educational specialist (ES). These 4 respondents were the main educational leaders within LED during the initial design, development and

implementation of the semester. They are still involved. The 5th respondent is the current overall project leader (PL), who got this role two years ago, when the semester was growing across faculties.

Each interview started with a number of general questions about interdisciplinary education and its design and implementation. Subsequently, respondents were invited to describe as concretely and detailed as possible how implementation occurred. After these general, open questions, the interviewer posed concrete questions derived from the three leadership practices, asking the respondents to specify their own role. Examples are (practice of managing educational program): What have *you* done or organized to support teachers while they were/are implementing the semester? What changes did *you* make in the curriculum to make the Semester part of it? How do *you* monitor the implementation and its results? What didactic means did *you* design to help teachers implement? To what extent did *you* decide to select teachers who fit the semester?

3.4 Data analysis

All interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim. Data were coded and analyzed with Atlas.ti. Codes for citations and fragments were directly derived from the conceptual framework [11], as provided in table 1. Each leadership practice got a key code, and the activities a subcode. Apart from these, codes were applied to fragments about the general history of the program and to the concept/definition of interdisciplinarity. After coding, all fragments related to the same code were compared and contrasted, resulting in the description of the results. Key statements are supported with a quote.

4 RESULTS

The goal of the study was to provide rich, descriptive information on both the design and implementation processes, and on the role of educational leadership in the program. These descriptions are provided in the following sections. We did not quantify the results other than counting how many quotations were coded with a specific code for each interviewee (see Table 2 for code frequencies), indicating which leadership practices interviewees were referring to most frequently, and showing what differences there are between interviewees, or what leadership practices got most or least attention.

Table 2. Code frequency per interviewee

Respondent	General		Managing educ progr.				Developing organis.				Developing people				Totals
	History of program	Definition / implem.	productive environm	Monitoring results	Feedback	Teachers to crc	Vision	Working conditions	Connecting to comm	Allocation means	Coaching teachers	Setting an example	HR-policy	promoting learning	
TL	0	14	4	4	0	1	14	4	0	0	9	0	0	1	37
ES	2	10	0	1	0	6	4	1	2	4	4	0	0	2	24
HT	3	14	0	6	0	3	4	0	1	3	1	0	0	3	21
RE	2	4	1	2	0	3	0	1	6	1	1	0	0	2	11
PL	3	7	2	3	0	3	9	6	2	4	2	0	0	6	37
Totals	10	49	7	16	0	16	31	12	11	12	17	0	0	14	130

4.1 Implementation process of interdisciplinary education

The start: According to the respondents, there is no concrete starting point for the implementation of the interdisciplinary semester. There were several initiatives which came together. Such as an education day within the faculty where teachers from different disciplines met, the ongoing question of management for a better integration of research in the educational program, the increasing interdisciplinary character of the research projects of staff. Several programs felt the need to work together more efficiently, combining research, design and development in their education programs. They just started doing so, and designed an interdisciplinary project for students, the living technology project.

When other programs from other faculties indicated that they would like to join this type of education few years later, the interdisciplinary semester was born. This also asked for more organization, and a project leader was appointed.

Working procedures: According to the respondents, the semester has 3 goals: collaborating professionally in an interdisciplinary team, researching and creating a product. Students are, however, judged primarily on the progress of their learning, rather than on the quality of the product, since research and design processes may be functional in itself but lead to no concrete end products. The collaboration process between students is important.

According to RE, while working on interdisciplinary projects, the focus for students is not so much on fully grasping and incorporating the knowledge and skills of the other disciplines, but on understanding that disciplines have an effect on each other and that the whole is more than the sum of its parts. Others indicate that it is important that students get to understand the terminology of each discipline, and that they try to understand what the other persons really means (ES, PL). This implies that students should be able to account for their methods and have social skills to collaborate with other disciplines (RE).

Ideally, the preliminary project description is formulated in such a way that it becomes clear that students from different disciplines/programs are needed to work

together. Current practice is that several of the projects provided by research groups have a strong base in one discipline (PL).

It is up to students to show that they are going to solve a business challenge, aligned with client's wishes (PL). It is important that students have an equal share in the project, preventing freeriding. They are being coached by a tutor, who coaches students on the process. "*The role of the tutor is to create a safe learning environment*" (TL). Although tutors should -ideally- guide the process as little as possible, there are large differences between tutors ranging from directing strictly to giving students the control (ES).

Since the number of programs joining the semester is growing, several (former) questions are being raised (again): should the supervisor and/or assessor be a specialist in the subject? How to assess interdisciplinarity? Can a tutor also be a client? Overall, tutors should guide the process in a questioning way. And many new tutors find this difficult (TL). Also, since the project is meant as a vehicle for learning, this means that not all projects end with a clear and working product. Some of the clients find this difficult.

The respondents indicate that this type of education represents the future of education. And it may need preparation in former years as well as a follow-up process in the 3rd or 4th year. But not all students and tutors are fully comfortable, using this form.

4.2 Managing the educational program (teaching and learning)

The creation of a productive working environment: The PL obtains all projects. It is important that students can work in projects that ask for knowledge from their own discipline. The TL indicates, however, that there is too much emphasis on administration and accountability. This prevents them from investing in the development of the semester, for example through further professional development of tutors or development of assessment.

Monitoring activities and results: Currently, the program committee acts according to the PDCA-cycle. The HT stresses the importance of in-between monitoring of tutors, but also of students. The RE indicates that after the first implementation of the semester, tutors had more time to monitor student progress intensively than nowadays.

With respect to the monitoring of students, assessors are still calibrating the level of assessment. It is an important step for the further development of the implementation of the vision of the semester. But this process is very time consuming. The interviewees do not know whether tutors are being monitored by their own supervisors or by team leaders.

Giving feedback to teachers based on observations of teaching processes: Overall, it is not common to supervise tutors during the tutoring process. Incidentally, tutors could share experiences, or a new tutor could join a more experienced tutor, to watch and learn, but there is no structure or culture in which leaders observe tutors and provide them with feedback on their tutoring process. Currently, there is a trajectory of voluntary intervention, in which only 10 tutors participate.

Allocating teachers and support staff to curriculum parts: The allocation part is fairly simple. The client is stakeholder of the project. Since tutors are supposed to only

coach on process, rather than content, they can be assigned arbitrarily to the project group.

4.3 Developing the organization

Developing a clear vision and goals: Especially the TL and the current PL mentioned the vision more often than the others. The TL stresses the importance of developing a clear vision. At the first implementation of the semester, this was done during an education day. Because of this process, all tutors involved shared this vision. Now that more programs are joining, the PL took the initiative to revisit the vision and write it down, reflecting the current situation. New tutors were and are not involved in this vision process. According to the TL, this is hindering the quality, because “*it creates a top-down structure and general allocation of people*”. It can lead to problems, when the meaning and vision are not communicated properly and that the professionals do not understand why which decisions were taken. According to TL, the key to success is to ask the professional how the education should be shaped. Creating the curriculum together is fundamental to success.

The strategic allocation of means and managing the school environment and working conditions: Now that the semester is growing, an interfaculty project team has been formed (ES), consisting of 7 people. All members have their own responsibilities such as assessment, matching, or tutor development. Tutors have four hours per week per group for tutoring, training, (voluntary) intervision, and contact with clients. According to the respondents, this leaves no time for further development of the semester. With respect to leadership, the TL stresses the importance of transforming the culture towards one with an atmosphere of trust. This also implies confiding in tutors, that they know what they do, since the success of the semester depends on the quality of the tutoring. “*It is, however, important to realize that not every teacher is capable of good tutoring and not every teacher is happy with this role. The selection of tutors is, thus, crucial*”. Also, it is important to have enough experts available, who can be consulted by the students during the project process.

Connecting the school to the community outside the school: The project assignments are issued either by industry or by university professors. Through such assignments, industries make themselves known to students. For all clients, it is important to realize that this is an education project, as a vehicle for student learning. Since some large programs joined the semester, it might mean that some of the students are assigned to projects that do not have a base in their discipline. Although “*it can be very refreshing to have those students in your group, [but] it implies that research groups or external clients should be somewhat flexible*” (RE). This might hinder the acquisition of new projects.

Given this background, several opportunities could be explored, according to RE, such as researchers serving as an intermediary for industry, or forming student groups around a theme and -as such- joining forces, or having two student teams working for the same client, fostering competition.

4.4 Understanding and developing people

Intellectually stimulating and individually coaching teachers: According to the PL, the formulation of a vision based on current practice, and further alignment of the goals, activities and assessment was very helpful for her and the teachers. The TL indicates the importance of paying attention to the different perspectives of the teachers involved on the vision. Teachers want to help and shape education, so this means

that they should be involved from the start. *“This is my main lesson: it does not help when you define something at the strategic level and ‘spread it out’ over the organization. I need to be there with my team, let them do that work, and support them” (TL)*. Teachers can come with questions or hurdles they are facing, but also for inspiration or to get other perspectives. It seems that teachers do so with their own TL, and less with the TL or the ES of the semester.

There are several people in, or around the project team, who have expertise on different elements of the semester. They organize single or group sessions with tutors, such as on research abilities, or on how to coach student groups. The quality of the coaching itself is not being monitored. The amount of interdisciplinarity can be traced from the portfolios of the students. And they show some diversity from multidisciplinary to interdisciplinarity.

Promoting (and participating in) teacher learning and development: All tutors attended three three-hour training sessions, that were focused on assessment, research abilities, and coaching. The training sessions consisted of knowledge transfer, as well as practice and inter-collegial coaching. According to the PL, the training sessions should be expanded, in order for tutors to be able to further develop their behavior as a coach. Building a learning community could be an option, as well as intervision. She acknowledges that half a day per student group is not too generous. The HT indicates that it is important for tutors to have a positive attitude towards learning. *“Tutors need to be willing to discuss their own frames of reference with each other and should embrace this as an opportunity for learning rather than framing it as an extra task”*. He regards it as risky when tutors stop reflecting on their own behavior with colleagues.

5 DISCUSSION

In this exploratory study, we held interviews with 5 key stakeholders who were involved in the implementation of the interdisciplinary Smart Solutions Semester. We focused on two questions:

- Within the faculty of LED, how has interdisciplinary engineering education been implemented?
- Within the faculty of LED, what were leadership behaviors, practices and actions in this process?

Overall, in Saxion, this semester started as a bottom-up initiative, with a unique and shared vision, was implemented enthusiastically by the teachers involved because they saw a real need for this type of education, and its implementation was judged as being successful by them. Other programs see its relevance and want to join. This matches with theory, indicating that bottom-up initiatives are more likely to succeed.

Now that the number of programs joining the semester is growing, the university board has appointed a special project manager to let it run smoothly, and is stimulating more programs to participate. With this upscaling, for the new programs, the semester has elements of a top-down initiative.

The interviews gave us detailed and in-depth information on current leadership practices. Activities were reported in all of the integrated leadership practices -though not equally- and we gathered information about challenges and successes, according to the stakeholders. In order to get a better understanding of the results, we conducted a short additional literature study. A comparison of our practice and the literature leads to several conclusions to be discussed in this paragraph.

5.1 Interdisciplinary education

The results show through the growth of the semester, that the idea of interdisciplinary education is attractive to an increasing number of programs. Since the number of people who were not involved in the original implementation is growing, it is time to rethink the concept of interdisciplinarity. The respondents concluded that not all of the project statements already invoke the body of knowledge from several disciplines. And, even when they do, some of the student portfolios show that they have worked as professionals, side by side, analyzing and solving the challenge without integrating the different perspectives. At the same time, there are examples of real interdisciplinary projects. So, it could be concluded that the semester is well under way, but further steps towards more interdisciplinarity can be taken. Since tutors, from the perspective of distributed leadership, have such an important role in living the vision and in implementing the concept, we searched in literature for cues. Here, we found that tutor behavior is crucial, in helping students to get to know each other's discipline.

The importance of getting to know each other's discipline: As the results show, in this interdisciplinary semester, tutors primarily coach students on process, rather than on content. Boon and van Baalen [12] came to similar findings, concluding that the focus in interdisciplinary projects is often on collaboration and communicative skills. As the student portfolios show, the outcomes of the projects can be called interdisciplinary but also multidisciplinary. It can be questioned whether coaching on only the project process is yielding optimal results. The core of interdisciplinary education is the integration of knowledge [12]. Reflective and metacognitive skills are important to understand each other's discipline, including the structure of underlying knowledge. Coaching students on these reflective and metacognitive skills might be more worthwhile, since it will help them understand the way in which knowledge in the different disciplines is being constructed, which is a first step towards integration of knowledge of interdisciplinary education.

The importance of the coaching role by teachers: Interdisciplinary learning can only be realized when learning is scaffolded adequately [5]. In the coaching role, tutors can question students, facilitate them, set boundaries between disciplines, and can help students formulate a good problem definition. Although tutors should -ideally- steer the process as little as possible, in this study there were reported to be large differences between tutors, ranging from directing strictly to letting students take control. At the same time, there is hardly any real-life information available about the tutoring behavior. Our respondents showed that teachers are not being observed and -thus- do not get feedback on their tutoring, and that their leaders do not seem to set examples by themselves. Other research on the semester shows [1] that teachers are indecisive about their role as coach, expert, or tutor. Currently, in a related research project, we are conducting a small study in which we observe ten tutors of the Smart Solution Semester in order to collect inside information about their tutoring behavior. It is an obvious suggestion to management to invest in tutor development, focusing on coaching skills, and maybe also on developing the right attitude for such activities, such as having a basic openness, willingness to work across boundaries themselves, etc. An important element in this could be the formulation of a clear HR-policy which is currently missing.

5.2 Educational leadership

Generally, we see that activities are being performed in all leadership practices, which lays the basis for success [8]. At the same time, apart from putting the vision to paper, the primary focus seems to have been put on formalizing the program and creating organizational conditions. In the process of scaling-up the semester, managerial and organizational aspects have prevailed. The leadership practice 'developing and understanding people' seems to have gotten less attention. Tutors have been offered a short training program, but more steps are needed with respect to providing tutors with good examples, setting up HR-policy, inspiring and helping them in their further development. There are poor insights into what is really happening in the sessions with students.

In the data, we see signs of distributed leadership, at least amongst the project team. Team members have different responsibilities in fostering the development of the semester. Teachers are then trusted to take over responsibilities during implementation, but interaction between tutors seems to be poor, and data on how the vision is being practiced is lacking.

The importance of a shared vision: Respondents indicated the importance of having a shared vision. This is congruent with findings from other research [13]. Whereas forming and practicing this vision was a bottom-up initiative at the start of the semester, now that it has grown, a steering committee has formulated the vision on paper for new tutors and programs. For some of them, this could feel like a top-down initiative. West (2014) indicates that it is important that the vision is clear and understandable, and shared by the teachers. Also, individual, professional relationships between teachers are crucial for the success of interdisciplinary education. In these interviews, it was reported that it is not natural for teachers to meet each other and it is also a challenge to get teachers with different interests and backgrounds in agreement. This aligns with others [13]. It is, thus recommended to the project team to invest in sharing, discussing and reliving the vision with new tutors. In our second phase of the research, we will more closely investigate this process in those faculties where new programs are joining the semester.

Since the development of the vision has such a central role in improving education, we adhere to Leithwood et al [8], who deliberately formulate the development of a vision as a separate leadership practice, rather than integrate it as one sub activity in the leadership practice of 'developing the organization', as Muilenburg et al [11] do.

The importance of developing the organization: Universities are complex organizations with several faculties and departments. They are often housed in different buildings. The physical location can thus be a natural barrier for people to meet. Moreover, implementing interdisciplinary education requires several managers or supervisors to support and approve the concept. As such, the formal organizational structure could be hindering the organization of interdisciplinary education [13]. Our semester is in a transition from being organized by its founding fathers to being organized by a central team, making choices that -naturally- cannot please every single person. The focus seems to have been on making central rules and arrangements. It is a general experience that the management of the participating programs is very supportive. As such, this part of the organization is not hindering the implementation. Where it becomes difficult, is the next step, spreading it to the teachers. Because, even when there are opportunities to meet, work and learn together, this does not happen automatically [13]. Also our results do not show

such natural inclination of tutors. This finding is congruent with findings by Busscher [1], who shows that tutors do not work together often. It was agreed upon by several respondents that the available time for teachers is scarce. This may be a hindering factor. Also, the (un)willingness of teachers to learn and reflect with each other might be hindering. From the concept of distributed leadership it could be argued that it is now up to teachers and their team leaders to make the next move.

6 RECOMMENDATIONS

This study has provided insights into the level of implementation of interdisciplinary education in the Smart Solutions Semester. Factors that were hindering or supporting implementation were detected and they were aligned with new and existing theory. Below, we end with several recommendations, derived from this study and its results. They might be of help for those who want to develop and implement interdisciplinary education.

6.1 Interdisciplinary education

- Interdisciplinary learning is often connected to working on real life projects. It requires not only coaching of students on the project process, but also on reflective and metacognitive skills, which are important to understand each other's discipline and to integrate interdisciplinary knowledge.
- A focus on interdisciplinary learning becomes more smoothly, when students are already familiar with working on projects in project teams in former parts of the curriculum.

6.2 Leadership practices

- All leadership practices need to be in place in order to realize a successful and sustainable implementation of interdisciplinary education. These may be distributed amongst different persons.
- Reserve ample of time and opportunity for teachers to discuss and share the vision in connection to their own views of interdisciplinary education. It increases the feeling of a bottom-up process, and its impact, even in a top-down situation. The key to success is to ask the professional how the education should be shaped. Creating the curriculum together is fundamental to success.
- Create opportunities for teachers to meet, work and learn together, in terms of sufficient non-teaching time or space (working space in the same building or on the same floor).
- At the same time, create an atmosphere that invites and stimulates teachers to build professional relationships with their colleagues, since teachers seem not to have a natural inclination to do so. An open culture, in which it is utterly normal for teachers to meet, observe each other and discuss their behaviors.
- Invest in teacher development through teacher training and intervision. The focus of teacher development should be on coaching skills for both process and knowledge (e.g. questioning students, facilitating them, setting boundaries between disciplines, and helping students formulate a good problem definition).
- Embed the teacher development in formal Human Resource Policy.

REFERENCES

- [1] Busscher, M. (2018). Een onderzoek naar Interdisciplinaire samenwerking tussen docenten binnen het Project Smart Solutions Semester van Saxion. Master Organisatie, Cultuur en Management.
- [2] Gast, I., Schildkamp, K., Veen, J.T. van der & McKenney, S.E. (2018), Different learning activities for different learning outcomes: University teachers' perception of learning in the context of collaborative curriculum design and implementation. (under review).
- [3] Truijen, K., Rikkerink, M., & Visscher-Voerman, J. (2018), Onderwijskundig leiderschap in het basisonderwijs. Leidinggeven aan onderzoekend en ontwerpend leren [Educational Leadership in primary education], *Schoolmanagement, Vakblad voor Management, Bestuur en Toezicht*, Vol 20, No. 3, pp. 24-28.
- [4] Graham, R. (2018), *The global state of the art in engineering education*, MIT, Cambridge.
- [5] Schuman, H. (2010), *Being a professional today means becoming interprofessional*, Fontys opleidingscentrum speciale onderwijszorg, Tilburg.
- [6] Stentoft, D. (2017), From saying to doing interdisciplinary learning: Is problem-based learning the answer? *Active Learning in Higher Education*, Vol. 18, No. 1, pp. 51-61.
- [7] Gresnigt, R., Taconis, R., van Keulen, H., Gravemeijer, K. and Baartman, L. (2014), Promoting science and technology in primary education: a review of integrated curricula, *Studies in Science Education*, Vol. 50, No. 1, pp. 47-84.
- [8] Leithwood, K. Day, C., Sammons, P., Harris, A. and Hopkins, D. (2006), *Successful school leadership: What it is and how it influences pupil learning*. Report RR800. University of Nottingham: National College for School Leadership.
- [9] Hendriks, M. A. and Scheerens, J. (2013), School leadership effects revisited: a review of empirical studies guided by indirect-effect models. *School Leadership & Management*, Vol. 33, No. 4, pp. 373-394.
- [10] Robinson, V., Lloyd, C. and Rowe, K. (2008), The impact of leadership on student outcomes: An analysis of the differential effects of leadership types. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, Vol. 44, No. 5, pp. 635-674.
- [11] Muilenberg, E.M., Poortman, C.L., Schildkamp, K., De Vries, S. and Van Veen, K. (in progress). *Leading data teams for sustainable school improvement*.
- [12] Boon, M. and Van Baalen, S. (2018), Epistemology for interdisciplinary research – Shifting philosophical paradigms of science, *European Journal for Philosophy of Science*, Vol. 9, No. 1.
- [13] McDonald, J.K., West, R.E., Rich, P.J. & Pflieger, I. (2018), It's so wonderful having different majors working together: The development of an interdisciplinary design thinking minor *TechTrends 2018*, pp.1-11.